

Principals' Instructional Leadership and School Effectiveness: The Mediation Role of Effective Teaching Practices in Secondary Schools of Pakistan

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ABSTRACT: In Pakistan schools performance can be improved by developing the performance principals as instructional leader. The instructional leadership smoothens way for school effectiveness through the effective teaching practices in schools because there is an indirect relationship between instructional leadership and school effectiveness in Pakistan. In this survey research, a conceptual model was developed to analyze school effectiveness and thereby aid “self-development” of education system in Pakistan without additional cost. Here, self-development of schools mean “applying this conceptual model by the school principals their selves, and not necessarily by the government” on the basis of what is learned. The aim is to answer the low quality of schools performance due to low educational budget. For this purpose, a total of 368 teachers were visited from 69 secondary schools of Mardan district (KP province, Pakistan). To analyze the data to find the relationship between the variables (school effectiveness, effective teaching practices, and principals' instructional leadership) predictive and descriptive statistic were used. It is evident from the result that the relationship between the variables is significant and strong, though the relationship between the instructional leadership and school effectiveness was found indirect. Also, age was not the moderator for the stated relationship. The results of the study provided evidence that effective teaching practices promoted by instructional leaders (principals) can make contributions to school development and productivity without any extra cost.